

Kamancin Jinsi a Sunayen Yanka na Hausawa da Wasu Harsuna (Larabci da Ingilishi)

Adamu Abubakar

Sashen Nazarin Harsuna, Kwalejin Kimiyya da Fasaha, Kaduna.

Gabatarwa

Daga cikin hanyoyi masu yawa da masana da manazarta suka danganta al'ummar Hausawa da Larabawa, akwai harshe, kamar yadda Greenberg (1947) da Schuh (1982) suka bayyana cewa Hausa da Larabci suna da nasaba, kasancewar, su jikoki ne na harshen Afro-Asiatic, wanda har ila yau ake kira da 'Hamu da Sanu', wato harshen 'ya'yan Annabi Isma'il (A.S). Haka kuma babu harshen da ya kai Larabci daraja a wajen Bahaushe, domin shi ne harshen Alkur'ani, kuma harshen da ake koyon addinin da shi, a cewar (Zarruk 1978). Alaƙar Hausawa da Larabawa ce ta sanya Hausawa aron kalmomin Larabci, baya ga haka kuma Hausawan suka koyi tsare-tsarensu na gudanar da makarantun Islamiyya da shari'a da siyasa da dai sauransu, a cewar (Yalwa 1994 :4-6). Musulunci shi ne addinin da yawancin Hausawa ke bi. Saboda haka daidai ne idan aka ce, akasarin tarbiyyar Hausa ma ta wannan addini ce.

A wajen musulmi, kowa yana da sunan yanka, wato sunan da aka raɗa masa bayan kwana bakwai da haihuwa, A nan ne akan bai wa yaro sunayen Manzo na yabo ko sunayensa na ƙidaya ko sunayen danginsa da alayensa da tabi'ansa da shaihunnai da Mala'iku da sauransu. Alhassan da wasu (1982 :26-27), duk da dai a yanzu akan samu wasu Hausawan da suke raɗa wa 'ya'yansu suna a ranar da aka haife su sakamakon wasu hujjoji da suke dogaro da su, saboda farin fahimta da ake samu a addini.

A ɗayan ɓangaren kuwa, shi ma harshen Ingilishi harshe ne muhimmi, domin shi ne harshen hukuma musamman ga al'ummun da ke zaune a ƙasashe, rainon Ingila kamar Nijeriya da Ghana da Liberiya da Saliyo da kuma yankunan wasu ƙasashe rainon Faransa, kamar Nijar da Kamaru da Chadi da Ivory-Coast da dai sauransu. Abin nufi a nan shi ne, Ingilishi shi ne harshe na ɗaya ko na biyu da ake amfani da shi wajen gudanar da gwamnati da makarantu da kotuna da kafafen yada labarai da dai sauran muhimman wurare na waɗannan ƙasashen. Har ila yau kuma, ɗaya ne daga cikin harsunan da Turawan Mishan (Missionaries) suka yi amfani da su wajen yada addinin Kirista (Christianity) a ƙasashen Afirka, wanda hakan ya sa mafi yawancin al'ummun da suka rungumi addinin Kirista suke sanya wa 'ya'yansu sunaye irin na Turawa, a matsayin sunan yanka ko kuma sunan laƙabi.

Manufar wannan makala ita ce fito da kamanci a cikin jinsin sunayen yanka a tsakanin al'ummar Hausawa, waɗanda suka samo daga Larabawa da kuma sunayen sauran al'ummu, waɗanda suka samo daga Turawa, ta hanyar amfani da ɗafi (affixation). Amma kafin a kai ga nan, za a yi sharar fage da bayanai a kan waɗannan abubuwa muhimmai kamar haka :

Hanyoyin Tattara Bayanai :

Hanyoyin da aka bi wajen tattara waɗannan bayanai sun hada da :

1. Amfani da Kamus na Hausa da Larabci da Ingilishi domin samun haske game da wasu sunayen yanka, musamman yadda ake furta su da rubuta su.
2. Amfani da littattafai da mujallu da muƙalu da nufin laɓuɓo muhimman bayanai da masana da manazarta sukayi waɗanda suka shafi wannan nazari.
3. Tattaunawa da masana da manazarta a harsunan Hausa da Larabci da Ingilishi da nufin samun muhimman bayanai da kuma tattaunawa da masana a ɓangarorin addinin Musulunci da na Kirista domin jin mahangarsu game da wasu sunayen yankan da aka yi misali da su a wannan nazari

4. Amfani da wayar salula da kuma kafar sadarwa ta (internet) domin samun wasu sunayen yanka na Larabci da Ingilishi.

Ma'anar Jinsi :

Jinsi kalma ce arariya daga Larabci, wato 'جنس', wadda ke nufin namiji ko mace. A Ingilishi kuma ita ake kira 'gender'. Crystal (2008:206), ya bayyana cewa jinsi a nahawu rukunin kalmomi ne da ke nuna azuzuwan maza da mata da kuma waƙanda su ba maza ba, kuma su ba mata ba', wato (neutral gender), kamar yadda shi ma Abdulganiyyu (2010:216) ya ce jinsi a Larabci ya kasu gida biyu, wato jinsi mai jam'antuwa, (إسم الجنس الجمعي) kamar: حمام - حمامة، تفاح - تفاحة، زيت - ماء، kamar: (إسم الجنس المفرد) kamar: زيت، ماء، زين، Jinju (1981:12-13), ya ce 'jinsi shi ne 'iri' na mutane ko waƙansu abubuwa'. Ya kara bayani da cewa, cikin Hausa ana raba halittu iri biyu; maza da mata, hanyar bambanta su ita ce wasulan ƙarshen sunaye. wasulan 'e' da 'i' da 'o' da 'u', na maza ne kamar: wasalin 'e' a kalmar jemage da kare da ƙarshe, wasalin 'i' a kalmar akushi da babi da buki da gari da hanji, wasalin 'o' a kalmar baƙo da fanko da kasko, wasalin 'u' a kalmar lemu da rumbu da gemu. Shi kuma jinsin mace, yawanci yana ƙarewa ne da wasalin 'a' kamar: kalmar abarba, soyayya, rowa, zakanya, duk da dai kuma ya ambaci wasu sunaye da suka ƙare da wasalin 'a' dɪn, amma kuma na jinsin maza ne kamar: ruwa, zakara, wata, boka da sauransu. Sai dai Galadanci (1976 :53) ya kara da cewa, kalmomin sunaye da suka ƙare da dafin 'iyaa' na jinsin mata ne kamar: falkiyaa da baturiyaa da barauniya da sauransu. Harshe da al'ada su ne suke zama jigon da ake amfani da su wajen samun kalmomi da suka dace domin sarrafawa cikin sadarwa, kamar yadda a Hausa, kowace halitta tana da miji da mata, saboda haka ne ma suke da zaki da zakanya, jaki da jaka (Yakasai 2020 :87).

Ma'anar Suna

Crystal (2008:333) da Skinner (1977:43) sun bayyana cewa suna wani rukuni ne na kalmomi wanda yake nufin laƙabin mutane ko wurare ko abubuwa, duk da dai, Ogundipe da wasu (1983:5) sun ce suna laƙabi ne na kowane abu. Su kuma Yahaya da wasu (1992 :1) sun ce suna kalma ce da ke nuna sunan abu, mai rai ko maras rai, wanda ake iya gani da wanda ba a iyawa. Wannan ya so ya yi daidai da bayanin Junaidu da 'Yar'adua (2007 :13) waƙanda suka ce suna kalma ce ta nahawu wadda ke bayanin suna ko laƙabin kowane abu, mai rai ko maras rai, mai motsi ko maras motsi, kamar yadda shi ma Aljarumy (1974 :16) ya ce suna shi ne duk wani lafazi da yake nuni ga ɗan-Adam ko dabbobi ko 'ya'yan itatuwa, ko sanƙararrun abubuwa ko wasu abubuwa na daban.

Rabe-raben Sunaye

A harshen Hausa da sauran harsuna kamar Ingilishi an karkasa sunaye kamar sunan yanka (proper noun) da suna gama-gari (common noun) da suna tattarau (countable noun) da suna gagara kirga (uncountable noun) da sunan tarayya (collective noun) da sunan ra'ayi (abstract noun) da gamafen suna (compound noun) da sauransu. (Junaidu da 'Yar'adua 2007 :13-19).

Sunan Yanka

A cewar Junaidu da 'Yar'adua (2007 :13) Suna na yanka ko zahiri, wato (proper noun), ɗaya ne daga cikin ire-iren sunaye, wanda shi ne ake kiran abubuwa kamar mutane da dabbobi da garuruwa da koguna da ƙasashe da bishiyoyi da duwatsu da sauransu. Yusuf (2011) ya yi bayanin cewa, sunan yanka suna ne da ake fara shi da babban baƙi, sannan ana amfani da shi ne kawai ga abubuwa na musamman, kamar Bala da Ladi da Kano da Libya.

Dafi

A fagen nazarin kirar kalma babu abin da ya fi ban sha'awa da burgewa, kamar dafi, a cewar Muhammad da Umar (2020). Kamar yadda Spencer (1991:14) a harshen Ingilishi ya ce, Affixation is morphology par excellence. Wanda za a iya fassarawa kamar: *Dafi a fannin nazarin kirar kalma wani abu ne mai matuƙa burgewa kwarai*. Masana na cikin gida a fannin kimiyyar harshe sun yi koƙarin fassara kalmar 'affixation' ta hanyoyi da dama, kamar yadda (Jinju 1980:6) ya fassara ta da 'karin ma'ana', Bagari (1986:165) kuma ya fassara ta da 'dofane', sai kuma Junaidu da 'Yar'adua (2007:70) suka fassara ta da 'doriya'. Sai dai mafi yawancin masana kamar Sani (2002:125) da Fagge (2013:4) da Bello (2014:70) sun rinjaya wajen fassara kalmar da 'dafi'.

Dafi turkakkiyar kwayar ma'ana ce (bound morpheme), wadda ke makale a jikin saiwa, a cewar Wardaugh (1977). Shi kuwa Matthews (1991:1) cewa ya yi dafi shi ne liƙa wani abu a jikin saiwar kalma. Katamba (1993:44), kuma ya ce dafi kwayar ma'ana ce wadda ba ta iya tsayuwa da kanta, har sai an jingina ta da wata kwayar ma'anar, kamar saiwar kalma ko tushen kalma, wannan bayani ya yi daidai da na Fagge (2013:4), wanda ya ce 'dafi kwayar ma'ana ce ta boye, wacce sai an dafa ta a jikin tushen kalma sannan ma'anar take bayyana'.

Rabe-Raben Dafi

Masana da dama kamar Matthews (1991) da Yahaya da wasu (1992) da Abubakar (2001) da Junaidu da 'Yar'adua (2007) da Abdulganiyyu (2010) da Fagge (2013) da Bello (2014) da sauran masana sun tafi a kan cewa dafi ya rabu zuwa gida uku kamar haka:

1. Dafa-goshi (prefix): dafin da ake liƙawa a gaban kalma
2. Dafa-ciki (infix): dafin da ake liƙawa a tsakiyar kalma
3. Dafa-ƙeya (suffix): dafin da ake liƙawa a gaban kalma

Duk da dai an samu wasu daga cikin masana da suka nuna shakku ko ƙin amincewa gaba-daya, game da samuwar dafa-ciki, kamar Alhassan (2011:11-12) a ɓangaren harshen Hausa da kuma Wardaugh (1977:88) da Katamba (1993:44) da Fromkin da wasu (2003:79-80) da sauransu a ɓangaren Ingilishi, bisa wasu hujjoji da suka dogara da su. Amma a ɓangaren harshen Larabci kuwa, wannan nazari bai yi kiciƙi ba da wani masani da ya yi musu ko nuna shakku game da samuwar dafa-ciki a harshen Larabci ba.

Sai dai dafin da ya shafi wannan nazari shi ne dafa-ƙeya, wanda Bauer (1983), ya bayyana shi da cewa shi ne mafi farin jinin dafi a harsunan duniya. Abin nufi, shi ne dafin da duk harsunan duniya suka fi amfani da shi wajen gina kalmominsu, wanda ya haɗa da sunaye.

Kwatancin Sunayen Yanka:

Dafe-dafen da aka yi amfani da su domin kwatanta sunayen yanka a Hausawa da sauran harsuna su ne dafin –aa da kuma dafin –iyaa kamar haka :

Dafa-ƙeya na -aa

Harsunan Hausa da Larabci da Ingilishi suna amfani da dafa-ƙeya na -aa domin samar da jinsin mace daga jinsin namiji a sunayen yanka kamar haka :

Hausa :

Jadawali na 1

Namiji	Namiji+ aa	Mace
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Hasan	Hasan+aa	Hasanaa
Husaini	Husain+aa	Husainaa
Haafizu	Haafiz+a	Haafizaa
Aadamu	Adam+aa	Adamaa
Mansuur	Mansuur+aa	Mansuuraa
Hamiidu	Hamiid+aa	Hamiidaa
Rabi'u	Rabi'+aa	Rabi'aa
Mashakuur	Mashakuur+aa	Mashakuuraa
Basiiru	Basiir+a	Basiiraa
Dawiilu	Dawiil+a	Dawilaa
Aziimu	Aziim+aa	Aziimaa
Jamiilu	Jamiil+aa	Jamiilaa
Aljanii	Aljan+aa	Aljanaa
Jaakii	Jaak+aa	Jaakaa

Larabci :

Jadawali na 2

Namiji	Namiji+ah	Mace
عَابِدْ Aabid	عَابِدْ+ة Aabid+ah	عَابِدَة Aabidah
حَنِيفْ Haniif	حَنِيفْ+ة Haniif+ah	حَنِيفَة Haniifah
عَقِيلْ AKiil	عَقِيلَة AKiil+ah	عَقِيلَة AKiilah
عَادِلْ Aadil	عَادِلْ+ة Aadil+ah	عَادِلَة Aadilah
حَمَامْ Hamaam	حَمَامْ+ة Hamaam+ah	حَمَامَة Hamaamah
قِطْ Kidf	قِطْ+ة Kidf+ah	قِطَة Kidfah
ثَعْلَبْ Tha'alab	ثَعْلَبْ+ة Tha'alab+ah	ثَعْلَبَة Tha'alabah
عَزَالْ Gzaal	عَزَالْ+ة Gzaal+ah	عَزَالَة Gzaalah
نِمْرْ Nimr	نِمْرْ+ة Nimr+ah	نِمْرَة Nimrah
ذَنْبْ Zi'ib	ذَنْبْ+ة Zi'ib+ah	ذَنْبَة Zi'ibah
قِرْدْ Kird	قِرْدْ+ة Kird+ah	قِرْدَة Kirdah

Ingilishi:

Jadawali na 3

Namiji	Namiji+a	Mace
Paul	Paul+aa	Paulaa

Emanuel	Emmanuel+ <u>aa</u>	Emmanuelaa
Manuel	Manuel+ <u>aa</u>	Manuela
Frank	Frank+ <u>aa</u>	Frankaa
Francis	Francisc+ <u>aa</u>	Francisca
Gabriel	Gabriel+ <u>aa</u>	Gabrielaa
Angel	Angel+ <u>aa</u>	Angela
Angelino	Angelin+ <u>aa</u>	Angelina
George	Georg+ <u>inaa</u>	Georgina
Justin	Justin+ <u>aa</u>	Justina
Christian	Christian+ <u>aa</u>	Christina
Morgan	Morgan+ <u>aa</u>	Morgana
Augustine	Augustin+ <u>aa</u>	Augustina
Albert	Albert+ <u>aa</u>	Alberta
Celestine	Celestin+ <u>aa</u>	Celestina
Luiz	Luiz+ <u>aa</u>	Luizaa

Kamar yadda aka gani a jadawula guda uku da suka gabata, harsunan Hausa da Larabci da kuma Ingilishi, sun yi tarayya wajen amfani da dafa-keya makamantan juna, wato -aa domin fitar da sunan yanka na jinsin mace daga jinsin namiji, duk da dai na Larabci ya dan bambanta, wato -ah wanda bai da tsayi wajen furuci, wanda kuma ake da damar furtawa ta hanyoyi biyu, ma'ana ko dai a furta karshen da 'tu' kamar *tha'alabatu* ko 'ah' kamar *tha'alabah*. Ka'idar harshen Larabci ce ta sanya ake furta 'ah' a madadin 'tu', musamman idan wata kalma ba ta biyo bayan kalmar da ta kare da 'ة' (ta rufaffiya) ba, wato *تَاءُ الْمَرْبُوطَةِ* (ta al- marbuḍah). Kamar yadda Abdulganiyyu (2010) ya yi bayani.

Amma duk da haka idan aka dora sunayen Larabci da Ingilishi a kan kirar rubutun Hausa, za a ga suna da kamanci kwarai kamar haka :

Hausa	Larabci	Ingilishi
Hasan <u>aa</u>	Haniif <u>aa</u>	Paul <u>aa</u>
Mashakur <u>aa</u>	Aadil <u>aa</u>	Franca <u>aa</u>

Idan kuma aka dora na Hausa da Ingilishi a kan kirar na Larabci, za a same su kamar haka :

Hausa	Ingilishi
Hasanah/Hasanatu	Paulah/Paulatu
Mashakurah/mashkuratu	Francah/Francatu

Dafa-keya na -iyyaa/iyaa

A nan ma harsunan Hausa da Larabci da Ingilishi suna amfani da dafa-keya makamantan juna, domin samar da jinsin mace daga jinsin namiji a sunayen yanka kamar haka:

Hausa :

Jadawali na 4

Namiji	Namiji+ ‘iyya/iya’	Mace
Badaru	Badar+ <u>iyya</u>	Badariyya
Shamsu	Shams+ <u>iyya</u>	Shamsiyya
Kamaru	Kamar+ <u>iyya</u>	Kamariyya
Aslam	Aslam+ <u>iyya</u>	Aslamiyya
Aabidu	Aabid+ <u>iyya</u>	Aabidiyya
Hannafi	Hannaf+ <u>iyya</u>	Hannafiyya
Bashari	Bashar+ <u>iyya</u>	Bashariyya
Ali	Al+ <u>iya</u>	Aliya
Hamiidu	Hamd+ <u>iyya</u>	Hamdiyya
Hambalii	Hambal+ <u>iyya</u>	Hambaliyya

Larabci:

Jadawali na 5

Namiji	Namiji+iyah	Mace
بَدْر Badr	بَدْر +يَّة Badr+ <u>iyah</u>	بَدْرِيَّة Badriyyah
سَعْد Sa’ad	سَعْد +يَّة Sa’ad+ <u>iyah</u>	سَعْدِيَّة Sa’diyyah
عَلِي Ali	عَلِي +ة Aal+ <u>iyah</u>	عَالِيَّة Aaliyah
سَامِي Saami	سَمِي +يَّة Sam+ <u>iyah</u>	سَامِيَّة Saamiyyah
نَادِي Naadii	نَادِي +يَّة Naad+ <u>iyah</u>	نَادِيَّة Naadiyah
أَحْد Ahd	أَحْد +يَّة Ahd+ <u>iyah</u>	أَحْدِيَّة Ahdiyah
عَبْد Abd	عَبْد +يَّة Abd+ <u>iyah</u>	عَبْدِيَّة Ahdiyah
عَافِي Aafii	عَافِي +ة Aaf+ <u>iyah</u>	عَافِيَّة Aafiyah

Ingilishi:

Jadawali na 6

Namiji	Namiji+‘iaa’	Mace
Victor	Vitor+ <u>iaa</u>	Vitoria
Anthony	Anthon+ <u>iaa</u>	Anthonia
Tony	Ton+ <u>iaa</u>	Tonia

Oliver	Oliv+ <u>iaa</u>	Olivia
Felix	Felic+ <u>iaa</u>	Felicia
Emile	Emil+ <u>iaa</u>	Emilia
Julius	Jul+ <u>iaa</u>	Julia
Cecil	Cecil+ <u>iaa</u>	Cecilia
Anastasius	Anastas+ <u>iaa</u>	Anastasia
Lucius	Luc+ <u>iaa</u>	Lucia
George	Georg+ <u>iaa</u>	Georgia
Alexandra	Alexandr+ <u>iaa</u>	Alexandria

Idan an lura da waƙannan misalai da suka gabata, za a ga cewa harsunan Hausa da Ingilishi sun yi kama ƙwarai, ta yin la'akari da yadda suka yi amfani da ɗafi, makamantan juna, wajen fitar da sunayen yanka na jinsin mace daga jinsin namiji. Harshen Hausa ya yi amfani ne da dogon daƙin -iyaa/iyyaa, Larabci kuma yi yi amfani da 'ة' (ta rufaffiya), wato تَاءُ الْمَرْبُوطَةِ (ta al-marbudah) wanda ake rubuta shi kamar 'iyah/iyah', yayin da Ingilishi kuma ya yi amfani da ɗafin -iaa.

A nan ma, idan aka ɗora sunayen Larabci da Ingilishi a kan tsarin rubutun Hausa mai amfani da ɗafin -iyaa, za a ga sun yi kama kamar haka :

Larabci	Ingilishi
Sa'adi <u>yaa</u>	Anthoni <u>yaa</u>
Sami <u>yaa</u>	Victori <u>yaa</u>

Idan kuma aka ɗora sunayen Hausa da Ingilishi a kan tsarin rubutun Larabci mai amfani da ɗafin -iyah/yatu, za a same su kamar haka :

Hausa	Ingilishi
Badariyyah/Badariyyatu	Anthonyah ko Anthoniyatu
Kamariyyah/Kamariyyatu	Victoryah/Victoriyatu

Kamar dai yadda Munir (2007) ya yi bayani da ya nuna cewa, idan aka bibiya, mai yiwuwa daga baya ne harshen Hausa ya koma furta kalmar baturiya a madadin baturiyatu, da barauniya a madadin barauniyatu da kuma tsuntsuwa a madadin tsuntsuwatu.

Idan kuwa aka ɗora su a kan tsarin rubutun Ingilishi, za a same su kamar haka :

Hausa	Larabci
Badari <u>a</u>	Sa'adi <u>a</u>
Kamari <u>a</u>	Samia

kamar yadda ya zo a Galadanci (1976:53) da Jinju (1981:7-8) da Fagge (2013:63) da Bello (2014:72-73) da Junaidu da 'Yar'adua (2007:24), duk kalmar suna ko sifa da ta ƙare da ɗoriyar 'iya' a Hausa, mace ce, kamar: *sharifiya, shakiyya, gajeriya, shudiya*.

Sakamakon Bincike:

1. Sunayen mata na yanka da aka fitar daga maza a Hausa, suna matsayin jinsin namiji ne kawai a Larabci, amma daga baya Hausawa suka fitar da jinsin mace daga jikinsu ta hanyar dafa musu dafin -iyaa kamar :

Kamariyya, daga قَمْرُ Kamaru (wata)

Badaru, daga بَدْرُ (wata)

Adamu, daga آدَمُ (Annabi Adam A.S)

2. Mafi yawancin sunayen da Hausawa suke rada wa 'ya'yansu a matsayin sunayen yanka, sun samo su ne daga Larabci, sakamakon cudanya da Larabawa.

3. Akwai wasu sunayen, wadanda a Larabci ake amfani da su a matsayin lafabi, ko sifa, ko kuma gama-gari, amma Hausawa suka mayar da su sunan yanka kamar :

Jamilu (mai kyau) - Jamila

Azimu (mai girma) - Aziza

Dawilu (dogo) - Dawila

Mashkur (mai godiya) - Mashkura

4. A bangaren sunayen Ingilishi kuwa, wadanda mafi yawanci mabiya addinin Kirista ne da sauran kabilun kasashen Afirka suke sanya wa 'ya'yansu a matsayin sunan yanka, sunaye ne da suka samo asali daga al'ummu daban-daban na duniya kamar Girka da Italiya da Latin, kamar :

Victor - Victoria (Latin)

Anastasius - Anastasia (Girka)

Lucius - Lucia (Italiya)

(<https://nameberry.com/baby-names/308/Names-Ending-in-ia-for-Girls>)

5. Akwai wasu sunayen yanka na jinsin mata wadanda ba daga jinsin namiji aka samar da su ba, kamar :

Hausa : Raliya, Alawiyya, Marakisiyya, Kursiyya

Ingilishi : Lydia, Cynthia, Alicia, Virginia, Prescilia, Mia.

6. Sannan kuma akwai sunayen yanka a Hausa da Larabci da Ingilishi, wadanda karshensu ya sa suka yi kama da na jinsin mace, amma kuma na maza ne kamar :

Hausa : Hamza, Ukasha, Usama Iliya (Ilyas)

Larabci Hamzah, Ukashah, Usamah

Ingilishi : Isiah, Irimiah, Elisha.

Kammalawa :

A ƙarshe, idan aka kalli waƙannan misalai da suka gabata, za a ga cewa lallai akwai kamanceceniya a sunayen yanka na jinsin mata da aka fitar daga jinsin maza, sakamakon dafe-dafen da harsunan Hausa da Larabci da Ingilishi suka yi amfani da su masu kama da juna, wanda hakan zai iya zama ƙarin hujja da ke nuna cewa, duk harsunan duniya, sun fito ne daga mutum ɗaya, wato Annabi Adam A.S.

Hakan kenan, yana nuna cewa, tabbas akwai hikimomi masu yawa a tattare da sunayen al'ummu na duniya, waƙanda masana da manazarta na Sassan Nazarin Harsunan Nijeriya da na Larabci da Ingilishi da sauransu, za su iya ci gaba da faɗaɗa bincike domin gano waƙannan hikimomin ko kuma wasu na daban.

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- Tattaunawa da Dr. Ahmad Umar na Sashen Nazarin Larabci na Jami'ar Jihar Kaduna a ranar 05/10/2021 da misalin karfe 12:00 na rana.

Tattaunawa da Dr. Khalil I. Adam na Sashen Nazarin Larabci na Jami'ar Jihar Kaduna a ranar 05/10/2021 da misalin ƙarfe 3 :15 na rana.

Tattaunawa da Mista Isiah Paul, Sakataren Cocin Bettelheim da ke, Kaduna Millenium City a ranar 21/10/2021 da misalin ƙarfe 10 :45 na safiya.

Tattaunawa da Ustaz Abubakar Auwal Usman, Mamba a Islamic Education & Civilisation Organization, Kaduna a ranar 3/11/2021 da misalin ƙarfe 6.00 na yamma.